

Mixing equilibria: The log K_M values for the following mixing equilibria 1–5:

work out to be 0.68, 1.48, 0.73, 0.34 and 0.85, respectively. In each case, a positive value of log K_M shows that the mixed complexes formed in equilibria (1)–(5) are more stable than the corresponding simple complexes.

Disproportionation equilibria: The following disproportionation equilibria (1–12) are involved in the various ternary systems,

The log X values for the equilibria (1)–(12) are –2.54, –1.4, –1.36, –2.96, –3.10, –1.46, –1.90, –1.42, –0.68, –1.7, –2.18, and –1.66, respectively. In each case, a negative value of log X shows that the mixed complexes are more stable than the corresponding binary complexes.

References

1. J. N. GAUR and V. K. SHARMA, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1968, **55**, 249.

2. D. R. CROW, "Polarography of Metal Complexes", Academic, New York, 1969, p. 166.
 3. J. N. GAUR and D. S. JAIN, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1965, **18**, 1687.
 4. D. I. KHOTSYANOVSKI and V. A. MOLODERASONA, *Moshnoster Tekhnol.*, 1965, **1**, 50.
 5. P. D. JADHAV and R. A. BHOSLE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 760.
 6. Y. KANEMURE and J. I. WATERS, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **29**, 1701.
 7. D. G. DHULBY, D. V. JAGIRDAR and D. D. KHANOLKOR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 2135.
 8. T. H. KADEN and S. FALLAB, *Chimia*, 1966, **20**, 51.
 9. J. N. GAUR and M. M. PALRECHA, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 589.
 10. S. C. KHURANA and C. M. GUPTA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **35**, 209.
 11. M. SHIVHARE and M. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 1599.
 12. M. SHIVHARE and M. SINGH, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1981, **30**, 277.
 13. M. SHIVHARE, KRISHNA, N. JAIN and M. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 2685.
 14. T. DEVIRES and J. L. KROON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2484.
 15. L. MERTES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience, New York, 1965, p. 227.
 16. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5312.
 17. J. J. LINGANE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, **29**, 1.
 18. W. B. SCHAAP and D. L. MCMASTERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4699.

On the Linear Free Energy Relationship

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THE importance and utility of the Hammett and Taft equations are well known¹⁻³. For the reactions of the type

We have $\log K = \log \frac{K_{\text{HA}}}{K_{\text{HR}}} = \rho\sigma$ (Hammett equation)

where HR=reference acid, HA=substituted acid ρ , known as the reaction solvent parameter at a particular temperature, measures the sensitivity of the reaction to electron supply or withdrawal, whereas σ , known as the substituent constant, measures the ability of the substituent to supply or withdraw electrons, σ is apparently independent of reaction, solvent and temperature⁴.

The extra-thermodynamic model proposed by Hepler and Hara^{5,6} shows clearly that the Hammett (or Taft) equation is more general than it ought to be. The thermodynamic functions have been written in terms of internal (intrinsic to the molecules and ions of the acid and base) and external or environmental (resulting from the interaction of the acid and base with the solvents) effects. Thus,

$$\delta \Delta H^\circ = \delta \Delta H_{\text{ext}} + \delta \Delta H_{\text{int}}$$

$$\text{and } \delta \Delta S^\circ = \delta \Delta S_{\text{ext}} + \delta \Delta S_{\text{int}} \approx \delta \Delta S_{\text{ext}}$$

since $\delta \Delta S_{\text{int}} = 0$ for symmetrical reactions of the type (1). Further, it has been observed that $\delta \Delta H_{\text{ext}}$ is proportional to $\delta \Delta S_{\text{ext}}$. Thus,

$$\delta \Delta H_{\text{ext}} = \beta \delta \Delta S_{\text{ext}} = \beta \delta \Delta S^\circ$$

$$\text{or, } \delta \Delta G^\circ = \delta \Delta H_{\text{int}} + (\beta - T) \delta \Delta S^\circ \approx \delta \Delta H_{\text{int}}$$

$$\text{or, } \rho \sigma = -\frac{\delta \Delta H_{\text{int}}}{2.303 RT} = \left(\frac{C}{2.303 RT} \right) \left(-\frac{\delta \Delta H_{\text{int}}}{C} \right)$$

The significance of the constant C has been discussed elsewhere⁷. The conditions for the linear free energy relationship to hold good are $\delta \Delta S_{\text{int}} = 0$ and $\beta = T$; obviously, deviations arise if the conditions are not satisfied due to change in the reaction mechanism or if resonance or solute-solvent interactions occur. Moreover, σ should be constant independent of the reaction and solvent only if $-\delta H_{\text{int}} \propto C$.

In spite of thermodynamic correlations, systematic and large deviations from Hammett equation have been noted due to its inherent limitations summarised as follows. (i) The Hammett equation is purely empirical and the σ values of substituents have been calculated taking the ρ value for the ionisation of benzoic acid in water at 25° to be unity. (ii) The equation lacks structural understanding of the parameters. (iii) The method of calculation of ρ is different for aliphatic acids. (iv) An important limitation arises in the use of the Hammett equation in the excited state and in solvents other than water particularly in mixed solvents. Since the variations of ρ with solvent systems as well as in the excited states are not known clearly, ρ values in mixed solvents or in the excited states are evaluated by using σ values in water in the ground state determined empirically. This obviously implies a constancy of σ values with solvents or in the excited states—a proposition which is unlikely to be valid. σ value is known to change with solvent⁹⁻¹¹. (v) Deviations in different solvents may arise from the different types of interactions like hydrogen-bonding which the substituents undergo with solvents^{12,13,16}. Solvent effects may arise from the differences in distances between substituent and reaction centre. The question of considering substituent together with its solvation shell may also arise. This means σ should change with solvents. (vi) Similarly, it has been shown that exalted σ values (σ^+ or σ^-) are needed to correlate the values in the excited states¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

The change in σ value can be explained from theoretical point of view as put forward by Dewar and Grisdale¹⁷. σ is dependent on direct electrostatic (or field) effect and mesomeric effect, *i.e.*,

$$\sigma = F/r_{ij} - M\pi_{ij}$$

where, F and M are constants determining the field and resonance effect, π_{ij} and r_{ij} are the atom-atom polarisability of the aromatic system and the distance between the points of attachment to the aromatic system of the substituent and sidechain, respectively. σ values would thus change in mixed

solvents due to change in field effects, and mesomeric effect would have little effect in mixed solvents. The change in σ value in the excited states is due to change of both field and mesomeric effects, the latter being more pronounced in the excited state.

The polar substituent constant σ^* in the Taft equation¹⁸ is widely used in case of aliphatic compounds using the relation,

$$\sigma^* = \left(\frac{1}{2.48} \right) \left[\log \left(\frac{k}{k_0} \right)_{\text{Basic}} - \log \left(\frac{k}{k_0} \right)_{\text{Acidic}} \right]$$

The reasons for the deviations from Taft equation^{4,12} are as follows. (i) The evaluation of σ^* necessitates the evaluation of rate data for both acidic and basic hydrolysis reactions at a single set of conditions. In view of the lack of such data, the σ^* values have been obtained at various conditions and averaged. The deviations of the σ^* values though small except when water is used have been observed. (ii) The evaluation of ρ^* and σ^* values of Taft equation were from kinetic considerations and not from thermodynamic one. The basic assumption that the steric and resonance effects are equal in the basic and acidic hydrolysis of esters is not always tenable as there are evidences for differences between steric effects on rates of acidic and basic ester hydrolysis^{19,20}. (iii) Deviations also arise due to intrusion of resonance effects, hydrogen bonding between substituent and reaction centre or steric effect, including conformational effect that change the relative orientations of the substituent and reaction centre.

The effects of substitution on the ionisation of acids or on the reaction rates are electronic in origin and three different modes of interactions are believed to be operative: field effects, inductive effects and resonance effects. Field effects (electronic effects) are transmitted through space. The exact calculations of the effects are extremely difficult in view of our inadequate knowledge of the distance from the reaction centre, the effective dielectric constants of the medium and a change in the dipole of the molecule due to substitution leading to changed solute-solvent interactions. Inductive effects are transmitted through bonds. The effect of substituents may alter the reaction mechanism due to resonance effects in various ways: (i) it may be by direct conjugation of a pair of electrons at the reaction site with the substituent; it requires exalted values of σ such as σ^- for proper fitting in the Hammett equation, and (ii) a new set of substituent constants σ^+ is defined for reactions which generate positive charge in a position capable of direct resonance interaction with the substituent, *i.e.* (Okamoto-Brown equation²¹),

$$\log \frac{K}{K_0} \left(\log \frac{k}{k_0} \right) = \rho \sigma^+$$

σ^+ values are obtained from the solvolysis of cumyl chloride at 25° in 9% acetone.

Thus, it is apparent that the Hammett and Taft equations lose generalisations if we change the value

of the substituent constant σ to accommodate the derived experimental values arising from different interactions. Rather, σ should have a specific value depending on the nature of the group, its distance from the reaction centre and the solvent in question. The change in ρ or C ($=2.303 RT\rho$) values using specific value of σ should indicate the change in reaction mechanism, resonance or other type of interactions. The magnitude of the interaction is equal to $(C' - C) \sigma$ cal, where C' is the value for the changed reaction solvent parameter and C is the value of the reaction solvent parameter where no change in reaction mechanism occurred.

In view of the limitations in the desired values of $\rho(C)$ and σ , it is desirable to derive the values of C and σ by other methods keeping the basic tenet of the linear free energy relationship in tact. With these objects in view, a method based on thermodynamic considerations^{7,9-11} to determine $\rho(C)$ and σ values, is suggested.

If we consider the reaction series of the type,

we have

$$X = \Delta G_{1(S)}^0 - \Delta G_{1(R)}^0 = -2.303 RT \rho_1 \sigma \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta G_{1(S)}^0$ and $\Delta G_{1(R)}^0$ are free energy changes for the substituted and unsubstituted compounds for the reaction series (1). For the second reaction series having the similar reaction mechanism and with similar substituents in the identical position, we have

$$Y = \Delta G_{2(S)}^0 - \Delta G_{2(R)}^0 = -2.303 RT \rho_2 \sigma \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Thus, } \frac{X}{Y} = \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2} = \frac{C_1}{C_2} \quad (C = 2.303 RT\rho) \quad (4)$$

The following procedure is suggested to calculate C and σ . To calculate C values of aliphatic acids, acetic and substituted-acetic acids, propionic and α -substituted-propionic acids were taken. Since CH_3COOH and CH_3CH_2COOH are similar except the CH_2 group and the nature of the reacting groups are the same, it is reasonable to assume that the difference in free energy changes (δ) between CH_3COOH and CH_3CH_2COOH would be totally reflected in the C values of the two series.

The increase in $\delta\Delta G_{int}$ suggests an increase in C values¹¹. With these assumptions, we have

$$X/Y = C_1/(C_1 + \delta) \quad (5)$$

From the free energy change of similarly substituted compounds of the two reaction series, one can have C or ρ values. The greater the number of compounds, the greater is the accuracy of the results. Once the C value for one set of compound is determined, σ values of the substituents could have been determined. The C (or ρ) values for acetic and propionic acids are obtained from the ΔG values (kcal mol^{-1}) of the following acids; acetic (6.48), propionic (6.65), bromoacetic (3.96), α -bromopropionic

(4.05), chloroacetic (3.91), α -chloropropionic (4.00) acids. The average value of C for acetic acid comes to be 5400 cal ($\rho=3.96$). Similarly, C value of propionic acid is 5570 cal ($\rho=4.09$). The σ values calculated from available substituted acetic acids are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Substituents	σ values	Predicted ΔG (kcal mol^{-1}) values for α -substituted-propionic acids
CN	0.576	3.44
F	0.546	3.61
Cl	0.476	—
Br	0.467	—
I	0.400	4.42
OCH ₃	0.300	4.98
C ₆ H ₅	0.111	6.04
OH	-0.091	6.82

It is true that very little light could be thrown due to paucity of data ρ value depends on temperature, reaction and solvent systems, *i.e.* the complex interactions it undergoes in solution. σ value represents the inductive effect on the substituents in the case of aliphatic compounds. It is to be noted in this connection that σ values obtained is almost identical to Taft's²¹ σ_1 (inductive) value. ρ value for aliphatic acids is reported¹² to be 1.72 compared to 3.96 obtained in the present study whereas the σ values obtained are more than twice the σ values. Thus, the conclusions in the present study are the same as that given by Taft.

Though ρ values have been widely used but the use of C values appear to be more realistic due to its greater sensitivity ($\rho=1$ means $C=1363$ cal) and the extent of deviation of the results could be better assessed⁷. ρ value has been taken to be the same σ (1.72) by Taft for all aliphatic acids whereas C values are clearly different for different acids

For aromatic compounds, both inductive and mesomeric effects are predominant. To calculate C and σ values of monocyclic aromatic compounds, similarly ΔG values of substituted-benzoic and 2-methylbenzoic acids, phenols and 2-methylphenols, anilines and 2-methylanilines (substituted by groups like CN, F, Cl, Br, I, *etc.* particularly in the 4-position) are to be used in the same way as suggested before. This would enable us to have an independent check regarding σ values which should come out to be the same from different systems under study. Unfortunately, lack of data stands in the way of calculating C (or ρ) and thus σ values in the aromatic systems.

The advantages of the method are (i) it is based on thermodynamic considerations, (ii) it is equally applicable to aliphatic and aromatic compounds without assuming any other condition, and (iii) it is equally useful in the evaluation of ρ and σ in the mixed solvents and excited states. It is, however, inopportune to say more without adequate correlation of data.

References

1. L. P. HAMMERT, 'Physical Organic Chemistry', 2nd. ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1970.
2. J. E. LEFFLER and E. GRUNWALD, 'Rates and Equilibria of Organic Reactions', Wiley, New York, 1968.
3. P. R. WEILS, "Linear Free Energy Relationships", Academic, London, 1968.
4. R. D. GILLIOM, "Introduction to Physical Organic Chemistry" Addison-Wesley, Philippines, 1970, Chap. 9.
5. L. G. HEPNER and W. C. HARA, *J. Phys. Chem. (Ithaca)*, 1961, 65, 811.
6. J. W. LARSON and L. G. HEPNER in "Solute-solvent Interactions", eds. J. R. COETZEE and C. D. RITCHIE Mircea Dekker, New York, 1969, Chap. 1.
7. D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Physik Chem. (NF)*, 1974, 88, 1.
8. W. I. BRIGHT and H. J. BRISCOE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993, 37, 787.
9. D. SENGUPTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Physik Chem. (Leipzig)* 1977 259, 1097.
10. A. K. MONDAL and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 495.
11. S. K. MAITY and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Physik Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1980 261, 573.
12. J. HINE, "Structural Effects on Equilibria in Organic Chemistry", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1976, Chap. 8.
13. R. W. TAFT, E. PRICE, I. R. FOX, I. O. LEWIS, K. K. ANDERSON and G. T. DAVIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 709, 3146.
14. H. H. JAFFE and H. L. JONES, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, 30, 964.
15. H. HRDLJVIC, D. BELLUS and M. LAZAR, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1968, 33, 59.
16. E. DE MEDICIS FRYTMANS and A. BRUYLIANT, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, 70, 10934.
17. M. J. S. DEWAR and P. J. GRISDALE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 3539.
18. R. W. TAFT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 8120, 1953, 75, 4231.
19. Y. OKAMATO and H. C. BROWN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 487.
20. N. B. CHAPMAN, A. ESHAN, J. SHORTER and K. J. TOYNE, *J. Chem. Soc., B*, 1967, 570, 1968, 178.
21. R. W. TAFT and I. O. LEWIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 5943.
22. R. W. TAFT in "Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry", ed. M. S. NEWMANN, Wiley, New York, 1956, Chap. 13.

Studies on *m*-Cresol - Formaldehyde Cationic Resins

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ION-exchange resins find wide range applications¹. Many of these resins are prepared from petroleum products, and attempts have been made to find out cheaper substitutes which retain all the properties of the parent resin. Vasudevan and Sharma² used sulphonated charcoal obtained from coconut shells and saw dust for the substitute. Phenol-formaldehyde was chosen as the polymeric matrix. They

showed that the substitution upto 30-35% does not lead to reduction in the chemical and thermal stability or the apparent exchange capacity for various ions. Based on this observation an attempt has been made to synthesise and study the properties of sulphonated *m*-cresol-formaldehyde, substituted partially by sulphonated charcoal obtained from *Bombox malabarica* fruit shell (considered as waste). *m*-Cresol was chosen to represent the phenol moiety as it appears to yield high cross-linking polymers.

Experimental

Concentrated H₂SO₄ (12.5 ml) was added slowly to *m*-cresol (10 ml) with constant cooling. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 3 h, then cooled immediately in ice and kept overnight. Concentrated H₂SO₄ was added to *Bombox malabarica* fruitshell and heated on a water-bath for ~6 h. Then it was washed free of acids and dried at 70°. Calculated quantity of the sulphonated charcoal was added to *m*-cresol-sulphuric acid so as to give percentage substitutions of 0, 10, 20, 30, 35, 40, 50 and 100. Each mixture was polymerised with formaldehyde (12.5 ml) at 70°, and the product ground, sieved and labelled as A, B, C, D, E, F, G and H.

Physical measurements: The absolute densities of the resin in the hydrated and dehydrated states were determined by using specific gravity bottle in water and in toluene (Table 1). The gravimetric percent swelling α was calculated from the equation,

$$\alpha = \frac{(M_w - M_d)}{M_d} \times 100$$

where, M_d and M_w are respectively the weight of dry and finally swollen resins. Swelling percentage for various samples are given in Table 1.

Attrition percentage: The percentage attrition of different samples was determined and compared with each other. The particles in each sample were separated into two sizes: > 200 and < 200 mesh. Particles greater than 200 mesh size were shaken for several hours, and again the particles greater than 200 mesh in size were separated. From the weights of the particles before and after shaking, the attrition effect was calculated for each sample, and the values were compared with each other. The percentage attrition of the composites are given in Table 1.

Exchange capacity: The exchange capacity of the samples for the exchange of Na⁺, Mg²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Ca²⁺ ions on the H⁺-form of the exchange were determined. The samples were converted to H⁺-form, test columns prepared in graduated burettes with cotton-wool plugs, known weight of the sample was made into slurry with distilled water and the burette column filled with the slurry. A 0.1 M sodium sulphate solution (20 ml) was added slowly to the column and allowed to pass at the rate of

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